

**PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE PROCESS
OF INCREASING YOUNG PEOPLE IN SOCIAL RELATIONS: PROBLEMS
AND SOLUTIONS**

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Abstract:

This article examines the pedagogical and psychological factors of the process of increasing the activity of young people in social relations. Ensuring the continuation of reforms in the social life of our republic and the formation of democratic civil society is connected with our youth, in particular with their social activity.

Key words: politics, age, iyyimai activist, transparency, young psychology, psychological medium.

Each area of knowledge has a unique name. But some of the knowledge field can also be called by a few names. For example, a young psychology can be called a way of development. But here is the introduction of knowledge very close to each other or each other in the field of knowledge, and human behavior, psychic development. Russian psychologist in its works in works, they are used as synonym.

The object of study of young psychology is a normal, change and development in ontogenesis.

The subject of young psychology is the age periods of development, the causes, mechanisms, ontogenesis of the age of the age, the directions, technologies, trends and overall laws.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Policy" "On State Policy" is set by: openness and transparency, participation of young people in the implementation of young people; spiritual, moral and The priority of cultural values; lib, it is more

related to this period. It is due to the serious construction of psychic processes, student activities. Therefore, adolescence requires strict changes in the organization of activities in the forms of relations. The difficulties for attaining adolescents are attempted Psychiatric development of children of this age blood The result is a result of not knowing or denying their bodies and properties sometimes. This period is much more useful to raise social activism. Because the child's marriage is difficult to become a major person, this process is seriously redeveloped by the form of treatment with people, and the change in living conditions and its activities. As a result, qualities begin to emerge, such as emergencies or rejection of adults. These cause difficult ", " complex "period of time. The difficulties in educating adolescents is that in the relations with the teenage, it is found to control its life and activities 'changes are important. It is necessary to find some new ways to influence them. Of course, it is advisable to treat the psychic development of schoolchildren in their activities. The new needs of the new need is to emerge and eliminate these needs. These contradictory is increasing physical, intelligent, intellectual and moral imcosity. The relationship between their intentions and their intentions is the way they are with their intentions Increased with old contradictions, community, adults and teams Raish Requirements These are the contradictions between the forms of rewards of adolescents. It is easier to be eliminated by being more highly highly leveling of mental development, complex activities and a number of new psychological qualities of the person. As a result, the psychic development of the teenager will be transferred to a stage. Disadvantages of defects, sensory bodies of the individual's biological growth, adversely affect the study, affects the development of social activeness.

The imperfections of the person, the emptiness of will, the weakness of the will, the weakness of the feeling, the absence of the necessary necessities and interests, the current ability to do the necessary need and interests, the ability to admire will noticed actions such as the media. Lack of negative amir morals against students to educate social activism; The teacher, class team, the misinterpretation of incorrect communication with family members, the proper distribution of free time and other adverse negative situations. Also, the shortcomings of the person's educational

activities: Inability to use methods of mental activity; My transactions, skills and qualifications are included in TAB activities: These include mistakes in teaching defects and activities. Defects in the influence of the environment, including pedagogical and psychological knowledge in the family, family conflicts, divorce, parental alcoholism. The influence of non-terminals, spiritual and educational development, will lead to an increase in difficult adolescents, the upbringing of the deficiencies in the public. The level of formation of the social activity of young people is determined on the basis of the following criteria:

- Having knowledge of worldviews enrichment and social relations: - Participation in the process of organization of social relations;
- and age, adequate skills in which they learn and use them in practical activities;
- Could be able to get out of problem situations and assess it:
- Namon harmonatively reflecting the level of social activity of students (qualityness, ideology, independence, independence, humanity, developmental, free thinking, creativity, felt trusting, the feeling of creativity, the feeling of creativity, responsibility)
- In the case of a state of view and others.

Criteria for social activism give discipline requirements and the importance of their importance, content. One of the main conditions for the effective training of social activism is the arrest, not only has a positive impact on the physiological functions of the body, and fulfilling discipline also contributes to the formation of skills and skills. Akh the psychological environment in the lesson is also important in improving social activism in students. The psychological environment of the lesson or m is a student and teacher's emotional emotional state. The "healthy microcime is still concerned pupils of the joy, 09 and the joy of the teacher, and the bruises of self-reliability, The fear does not exist without being available, and it always notes that the sense of self-confidence, teacher, and classmate, and the teacher's demand is also a testament to a healthy environment.

Conclusion that it is a key condition for the child's conduct, and the formation of its actions is consciously responding to the person, community, other people and It is important to say it's important that it is useful and necessary.

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